

OrganKits project

OrganKits partners have been working on the project and have several updates to share! The first OrganKits developed are presented in this 2nd newsletter. Want to find more? Contact us or visit our website

Top stories

Neumohealth & Environment

Neumohealth and its relationship with the Environment

The main topic of the educational guide created by our institution deals with the topic of Neumohealth and The Environment. The Steam and Project based approach was...

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Is there a correlation between musculoskeletal length and athletic performance?

It goes without saying that sport is crucial for a healthy life, but there are plenty of different factors that can affect our sports performance.

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Can a healthy brain nurture mindfulness?

Definitely yes! A healthy brain can support mindfulness by enhancing your ability to stay attentive, regulate emotions and maintain clarity of thought which are all important for cultivating mindfulness...

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How nutrition affects our wellness? - A holistic learning approach

The educational guide developed by Platon school's team aims to provide students a complete learning experience about nutrition and stress its importance to our wellness.

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